

Web platform and App

SPOKE N 4 – Montagna Digitale e Sostenibile

DELIVERABLE N7 INTERFACE

RM2 - Competitiveness of economic activities and valorization

of natural and cultural assets in mountain and remote areas

Version history

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Glossary

	Definition
Hub Coordinator (HC)	The Hub Coordinator represents the single point of contact for the implementation of the innovation ecosystem towards the MUR. It carries out the management and coordination activities of the innovation ecosystem, receives the fundings, verifies, and transmits to the MUR the reporting of the activities carried out by the Spoke and their affiliates.
National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP)	This document uses the Italian acronym for the NRRP, which is PNRR (Piano Nazionale della Ripresa e Resilienza)
Research Program Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the NODES project. The NODES will appoint the Research Program Manager. It refers to “Responsabile del Programma di Ricerca” in the MUR’s Call of proposal for “Ecosistemi di Innovazione”
NODES’ Research and innovation program	NODES’ Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spoke, with the aim to promote and support applied research on topics consistent with the Intelligent Specialization Strategy, with the guidelines of the 2021-2027 partnership agreement scheme, with regional operational plans and regional and national research and innovation priorities. Although NODES’ Spokes are concentrated on different themes, they will organize their activities and actions within a common framework – NODES’ Booster Methodology
Spoke Coordinator	The University in charge of coordinating the Spoke’s ecosystem. It refers to “Spoke” in the MUR’s Call of proposal for “Ecosistemi di Innovazione”
Spoke Data Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the monitoring and management of data generated at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Data Manager.
Spoke Partner	The entity associated to the Spoke Coordinator. It can be an Innovation Cluster, Competence Center, Research Center related to the Spoke’s ecosystem and contributes to achieve objectives and impact under the Spoke’ leadership and management. It refers to “soggetti affiliati” in the MUR’s Call of proposal for “Ecosistemi di Innovazione”.
Spoke Project manager	The person who will be the responsible for the management, coordination and progress of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Project Manager.
Spoke research and innovation program	NODES’ Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spokes. The spoke will leverage a consolidated collaboration with leading private and public companies and will focus the applied research activity on technological domains and applications that can favour the integration of SMEs into new value chains.
Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager.
Spoke Stakeholders Committee (SC)	Consultation structure formed by relevant stakeholders (Government, universities, companies, civil society, third sector, etc.)
Spoke Thematic	General target focus and domain of the Spoke research.
Spoke Topics	Specific areas/lines of development within the Spoke.
Spoke Work Package Leader	At the Spoke level, Work Packages (WPs) will be organized by WP leaders, who will be responsible for performance evaluation and reporting.
Flagship Project	Main research project at the Spoke level with the goal of prototyping, testing, demonstrating the research activities towards higher TRLs.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Research teams at the University of Turin and the Polytechnic of Turin have been working on building a web platform for data and digital content visualization. The platform includes three main types of content: a database of socio-economic indicators for municipalities, an open data hub, and a section for digitized content such as photographic archives. The Unito group is also planning digitalization courses for specific sectors (e.g., hospitality, catering, agri-food) based on a needs analysis. The platform is designed as a digital environment for the "Interface" flagship project, part of the Nodes ecosystem. It is currently in a testing phase to improve its appearance, identify any issues, and upload more content. Users will navigate the platform's home page to access sub-sections, including topics like valleys, data, training, and news. There's also a dynamic feature that allows users to explore content by individual valleys and access information about specific regions and municipalities. Additionally, the platform includes dashboards for dynamic data visualization, where users can view data, generate charts and maps, and select digital elements (e.g., images, videos, GPS tracks). The platform links directly to the Nodes Hub website for related news and announcements, and users can subscribe to the Nodes newsletter.

A. Introduction: Content Management Systems for data and digital content visualization

This section summarizes the overall objectives of the deliverable and provides an explanation of the type of web platform chosen

The research groups from the University of Turin (Unito) and the Polytechnic of Turin (Polito) have been collaborating to build a web platform aiming at collecting, systematizing, and making accessible data and digital content developed in the various stages of the research agenda of Research Module 2. Accordingly, the web platform is expected to provide a digital environment for the following types of input:

- (i) A database of socio-economic indicators for each municipality in the study area.
- (ii) An open data hub (e.g., hiking trails, cultural infrastructure, etc.).
- (iii) A section for digitized content (e.g., photographic archives). The Unito group is also proceeding with the planning of digitalization courses (sectors such as hospitality, catering, and agri-food) through a needs analysis phase via surveys and focus groups.

Content Management System (CMS) web platform

A Content Management System (CMS) is a software platform that allows users to create, manage, and modify digital content on a website. It typically provides an interface that enables easy management of text, images, videos, and other multimedia elements. When it comes to data visualization and digital content visualization, a CMS can serve as the backbone for presenting information in an intuitive and engaging way.

Data Visualization in a CMS:

CMS offers several advantages for the development of web applications, such as integration with data sources (pull in data from various sources - spreadsheets, databases, APIs - and turn it into interactive charts, graphs, or dashboards), customization (how data is displayed), interactivity (interactive visualization), embedding and sharing (data visualizations can be embedded within pages, and potentially export options for data stories).

Digital Content Visualization in a CMS:

CMS are also suitable with different forms of digital content visualization, for it provides multimedia support (offering the possibility for hosting infographics, video explainers, and articles all in one place), enhanced user experience (including themes, templates, and widgets that are optimized for presenting visual content in a user-friendly and visually appealing way, thus making digital content accessible and engaging for the audience), dynamic layouts, and performance optimization (for better user experience and SEO)

The research team decided to implement a CMS web platform because it allows users to present complex data or multimedia-rich content in a more engaging, digestible format, enhancing the user's experience and helping to make the data or content more understandable and accessible.

B. Web Platform Prototype

This section describes the main feature of the prototype of web-platform that has been implemented

The web platform has been designed as a digital environment for flagship project 3 'Interface,' which is part of the Nodes project Hub site (<https://ecs-nodes.eu/4-montagna-digitale-e-sostenibile/spoke-4-flagship-projects/progetto-interface>). Currently, the platform is in a testing phase to improve the coordinated image, evaluate any malfunctions, and continuously upload content. Figure 1 shows the appearance of the platform's 'home page,' from which the user can easily access the site's sub-sections (valleys, data, training, news) and the Nodes project Hub site, simply by clicking on the logo.

Fig. 1. Web Platform - Homepage

Designed to be a dynamic container of information and digital content, the site offers an overview of the topics covered, with the possibility for the user to select the sub-theme of interest. By clicking on one of the proposed icons (Figure 2), it will be possible to access the site's sub-sections.

Fig. 2. Web Platform - Directories

For a quick view of content related to specific geographic contexts, the site offers the option to view content by individual valley (Fig. 3). By selecting a valley of interest, the user is directed to a page containing information about the valley itself, as well as a list of municipalities (which can also be selected) that are part of it.

Fig. 3. Web Platform –Valleys

The dynamic aspect of navigation is ensured by the presence of dashboards (Fig. 4), through which the user can view data, create charts and maps, or select digital elements (such as images, videos, GPS tracks) of their interest.

Fig. 4. Web Platform - Dashboard

Finally, through the web platform, the research groups will be able to channel and make accessible the research and action programs designed together with the territories involved in the research. In the section 'Engagement of stakeholders in the mountain area' (Fig. 5), it will be possible to find both the planned and completed actions, along with summaries of the activities and the research or educational materials developed. This section is also directly linked

to the 'News' section of the Nodes Hub website (<https://ecs-nodes.eu/news>), where news and announcements related to the Interface activities will be posted.

Fig. 5. Web Platform - Activities

The platform thus represents a virtual environment where the different outcomes of the Interface research project can be channeled, while also providing a direct link to the activities, news, and results of the Nodes ecosystem. For completeness, the platform will also enable users to subscribe to the Nodes newsletter directly from the implemented platform itself.